

1. Translating Amara and Crowdin contents parallelly

Description: Currently, the stakeholders firstly translate the Crowdin content, then move on to the Amara content. Translators on each team can work separately, and thus Amara team does not need to wait for the Crowdin team to finish their part. Thus, Crowdin and Amara team can translate parallelly.

Justification: In order to translate the Crowdin content, the stakeholders spend **14137,65 minutes** each time, while this duration is **20199,8 minutes** for the complete translation of Amara content. The total time to finish the translation on both platforms would take around **34337.45 minutes**. Hereby, we consider the **Heuristic 5: Parallelism enhancement**.

Result: By translating the content on both platforms simultaneously will be around **20199.8 minutes** which is the maximum duration that is spent to translate the Amara content, and when the Amara team finishes the translation, then the Crowdin team would have finished their translation earlier. By doing this, the total duration will be decreased from **34337.45 minutes** to **20199.8 minutes**.

2. Text on the video screen to be translated on Amara

Description: While translating the script of videos, translators ignore the part about the text on the screen of the video, and this leads to a decrease in the quality of videos. In order to solve this problem, we can add the new column on Google Sheets of the team, and the translator can add the text on the screen there. These texts are generally short (4-6 sentences), and it would not create complications on Google Sheets.

Justification: 64% of Khan Academy Azerbaijani users visit the platform in order to watch videos rather doing exercises. Adding this column will directly improve the quality of the videos because the proofreader will detect more problems compared to now. Moreover, the possibility of having videos with problems will decrease **by 10% roughly**, and the proofreading process will be faster since the possibility of possessing errors will decrease from 40% to 30%. Furthermore, while controlling the quality of the videos, the quality control team will control **about 5% faster**. By doing this alteration, we referred to **Heuristic 9: Automation**.

Result: In conclusion, the quality of the videos will increase, and proofreading on Amara will be done within **144 minutes** less than it used to be, and the quality control team will also control **286.94 minutes** faster.

3. The same proofreader is responsible for proofreading the same content on Amara and Crowdin

Description: On the Khan Academy platform, the content on Amara and Crowdin is the same, however, the responsible proofreaders are different. Thus, sometimes proofreaders might utilize the terminology differently, and it increases the workload of the quality control team. Nevertheless, if the same person is responsible for both Amara and Crowdin content, then there will be the same terminology or the names used both in videos and exercises.

Justification: Around 11% of errors on the “Control quality” subprocess take place due to mistakes by proofreaders. Hereby, the main mistakes were about using the different terminology, names. These mistakes can be decreased up to 0.5% roughly since the mistakes are about using different notions, rather than wrong ones. Furthermore, it will also again help to increase the quality of videos. By unassigning one of the proofreaders, we refer to **Heuristic 7: Resource optimization**.

Result: As a result, we expect the quality control team to encounter **10.5% fewer mistakes** since all the terminologies or names will be proofread by the same person, and since the quality of videos will be much better, it will impact the learning experience of students positively.

4. Training Crowdin proposals before the localization

Description: It is possible to train the algorithm of the Crowdin platform in a way that proposes the correct terminology. In order to this, it will be enough to make the list of terminologies in English, and their translation into the Azerbaijani language.

Justification: While translating on the Crowdin platform, the Crowdin translator will have a chance to translate **10% faster** because instead of searching the translation of the terminology they will be able to get it through Crowdin’s proposals. Secondly, it will also decrease the number of mistakes made on Crowdin by 1% roughly, and this will help the proofreader spend finish proofreading **15% faster**. Subsequently, it will also increase the quality of exercises on the platform, since the proofreader will be able to detect even minor mistakes. With this proposal, we referred to the **Heuristic 9: Automation**.

Result: By implementing this proposal, the Crowdin translator will spend **261.3 minutes** less to translate, and the proofreader will spend **1832.2 minutes** less to proofread. Last but not least, it will also let the students have a better experience within the exercises part of the platform.

5. Eliminating both coordinators and project manager within all problem-solving issues

Description: When there is a problem, the translators get in touch with the coordinators, however, the coordinators are only delivering the same issue to the team leader, and thus the coordinators can be removed from the process (happens in the “Translate Crowdin Content”

and “Translate Amara Content” subprocesses). Similar to the previous issues, the dubber needs to communicate with the project manager in order to inform the problem of the translator, and hereby, the project manager can be removed from the process since he only informs the exact problem (“Recreate videos”).

Justification: In the “Translate the Crowdin” subprocess, the team wastes **122 minutes** because of the Crowdin coordinator and the project manager, and this duration is **5688 minutes** in the “Translate the Amara content” for the same reasons. From the perspective of the “Recreate videos” subprocess, because of the project manager, the team wastes **3308 minutes** in general. With this proposal, we refer to the **Heuristic 1: Task elimination**.

Result: As a result, the team will save **9118 minutes** in general within the localization process.

6. Mapping the videos through a code

Description: While mapping the videos on the Khan Academy Database, the Language Advocate can use the basic coding to map the videos, and if there are any, the to detect the missing videos as well. This basic coding can be improved by one of the team members since she has proposed to make this change.

Justification: In order to map the videos, the Language Advocate spends **392.6 minutes**, and within mapping, there are always missing videos that cannot be found easily in 45% of all cases. By using this basic coding, this percentage will be decreased to 5% roughly since all the missing videos will be shown directly. In addition to this, the Language Advocate will spend **205.4 minutes** mapping videos. In this proposal, we considered **Heuristic 9: Automation**.

Result By implementing this change, the “Deliver video” subprocess general cycle time will decrease from **3576.6 minutes** to **3389.4 minutes**, and it will accelerate the localization process.

7. The entire quality control team gives one feedback document

Description: Currently, the Language Advocate, Content Specialist, and Project Manager give the three different feedback and edit proposals to the Video Editor, and he needs to change it three times. However, the Language Advocate, Content Specialist, and Project Manager can work on the same document, and send only one editing feedback to the Video Editor.

Justification: The Language Advocate spends **1892.4 minutes** to review the content, and give feedback, and this duration is **3331.6 minutes** for the Content Specialist and **197.8 minutes** for the Project Manager. Moreover, the Video Editor spends **92.4 minutes** editing the Language Advocate’s editing proposals, **2281 minutes** editing the Content Specialist’s editing proposals,

15.8 minutes editing the Project Manager's editing proposals. However, this duration can be around three times less when he gets the document from all of these three stakeholders at once. Hereby, we refer to the **Heuristic 2: Task composition**.

Result: As a result of this change, the cycle time of the "Control quality" subprocess will decrease from **5783.8 minutes** to **1505 minutes**.

8. Using the video finding tool on Amara

Description: Finding some videos on Amara is quite hard, and Khan Academy Czechia team member Danial has developed a tool to find the videos on Amara. Utilizing that tool can help the stakeholders to find the video faster.

Justification: The Amara Translator spends **2767.8 minutes** to find the video on Amara, and it happens with 35% frequency. While using this tool, this percentage will decrease up to 2% roughly. Furthermore, it will also help us decrease the stress of frustrated translators. With this proposal, we refer to **Heuristic 9: Automation**.

Result: In conclusion, the "Translate Amara Content" cycle time will be **1186.2 minutes** shorter, because it will decrease from **2767.8 minutes** to **1581.6 minutes** and the Amara translator will be more motivated since the error rate will be 33% less.

9. Increasing the number of proofreaders

Description: There are only two proofreaders for the Math content, and some of the translators have enough experience and knowledge to be a proofreader. Upgrading the positions of four well-experienced translators position from translator to proofreader will help to speed up the localization process.

Justification: There are four people in the team who work as a translator, nevertheless, they can also perform the tasks of the proofreader, thus upgrading their position to the "proofreader" level will increase the proofreading process four times faster. We considered **Heuristic 7: Resource optimization**.

Result: In conclusion, the proofreading will be done four times faster.

10. Software key access is given to the Video Editor

Description: The video editor will have access to the internal communication board where the software key is updated. And instead of the Video Editor getting in touch with the Project Manager each time to get the software key in order to use the video editing software, he will be able to access it through this board if it is needed.

Justification: The Video Editor wastes **290.2 minutes** to get the software key, however, by implementing this change he will not wait for this, and he will be able to access the software key on his own. With this proposal, we refer to **Heuristic 8: Communication optimization** and **Heuristic 1: Task elimination**.

Result: As a result of this change, the “Recreate videos” subprocess will be performed **290.2 minutes** shorter duration.

ID	Proposal	The reason why we have not implemented
1	There should be the same translator on Amara and Crowdin. <i>(Amara proofreader, Interview 12)</i>	Since the translation on Amara is harder, the same translator can perform worse, and it can decrease the quality of videos. <i>(Language Advocate, Interview 3)</i>
2	Informing translators about using strings, Amara before starting their volunteering. <i>(Crowdin Coordinator, Interview 4)</i>	This research aims to optimize the localization process, and since this proposal is about the hiring/ onboarding process of the team, we could only inform the Volunteering Experience team about these issues.
3	Hiring volunteers should be more strict. <i>(Crowdin translator, Interview 12)</i>	This research aims to optimize the localization process, and since this proposal is about the hiring/ onboarding process of the team, we could only inform the HR team about these issues.
4	The translation proposal on Crowdin should be deleted. <i>(Crowdin translator, Interview 12)</i>	This is one of the core features of Crowdin, and some translators use it efficiently to finish their tasks. So instead of removing this feature, we trained an algorithm in a way that proposes the correct translations. <i>(Interview 15, Project Manager)</i>
5	Videos should be categorized on Amara. <i>(Amara translator, Interview 13)</i>	The possible implementation of this proposal requires a longer time period with the Amara team, and thus we could inform this feature as a proposal only.
6	Videos should be assigned by the coordinators. <i>(Team leader, Interview 14)</i>	In order to be able to assign the tasks, the user needs to have a “Language Manager” role which can be only assigned to a few people who work with the team for a longer timeframe, otherwise, it can cause complications within the team. <i>(Language Advocate, Interview 3)</i>